

Pangasinan State University Stakeholders' Awareness, Acceptance and Perception towards the Institutional Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives as Basis for Sustainability

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Abstract

This study assessed the level of awareness, acceptance, and perception of stakeholders at Pangasinan State University (PSU) Asingan Campus toward its Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) as a basis for institutional sustainability. Data were gathered from 365 stakeholders, including students, faculty, non-teaching staff, alumni, parents/guardians, and government agency partners using a descriptive survey method. Due to pandemic-related constraints, a modified and validated instrument was administered via Google Forms. Data analysis through SPSS revealed that most stakeholders were aware of the VMGO, with mean ratings falling within the "aware" to "highly aware" range. Acceptance levels were similarly high, with stakeholders expressing agreement and strong agreement toward the clarity, consistency, and relevance of the VMGO to institutional mandates and student outcomes. Notably, dissemination practices, such as posting VMGO on bulletin boards and online platforms, were generally effective but identified as areas needing enhancement. The study concludes that stakeholders are generally aware, accepting, and positively perceive the VMGO. Recommendations include strengthening dissemination strategies through broader media engagement and ensuring continuous stakeholder involvement in sustaining and internalizing the university's vision and mission.

Keywords: *Globally competitive, opportunities, professional advancement, periodic review, instructional effectiveness*

Introduction

The Pangasinan State University envisions becoming an ASEAN premier state university on 2025. With its mission, through instruction, research, extension, and production, commits to develop highly principled, morally upright, innovative and globally competent individuals capable of meeting the needs of industry, public service and civil society.

A state-supported institution such as the Pangasinan State University shall gear their programs to national, regional, or local development plans. Therefore, the PSU Asingan Campus Goals and Objectives are as follows: (1) to produce to globally competitive teachers, technicians, entrepreneurs and information technology professionals; (2) to provide opportunities and democratize access for the poor but deserving students to acquire quality education and make them productive citizens through intuitionally-funded and privately sponsored scholarship program; (3) to continuously upgrade the competencies of the faculty and professional advancement through scholarships, study grants, seminars and trainings; (4) to conduct periodic review of existing curricula and design and develop relevant and responsive programs that will meet the needs of the local and global community; (5) to conduct researches to improve instructional

effectiveness and to generate new technologies and perspectives; (6) to strengthen the extension services to enable the out-of-school youths, unemployed adults, potential entrepreneurs, and the women sector to acquire the necessary skills and attitudes for greater productivity; (7) to establish and strengthen linkages with the public and private agencies/ institutions for the realization of the campus programs; and (8) to conduct periodic evaluation and review of the management systems and processes for more efficient and effective campus operations.

The Area 1: Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives is the heart of the Program accreditation process of the AACUP. As cited in the Accreditation instrument, everything in the institution is justified only to the extent that it realizes its vision and mission. It is essential therefore, for the Pangasinan State University Asingan Campus, to formulate the vision and mission which should be the bases of all its operations. The Institution is judged by the degree to which these are attained, not in comparison with others.

The institution's vision, mission, goals and objectives serve as the compass on where it's heading. It is where to anchor the plans, policies, programs, and activities to realize its purpose as an institution of higher learning. Therefore, it is important to measure the extent of awareness, understanding and acceptance of the Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the level of awareness, acceptance and perception of PSU Asingan faculty, staff, students, parents/ guardians, alumni, and other government agency partners towards the vision, mission, goals and objectives. Specifically, it aims to (1) determine the level of awareness of the stakeholders towards the VMGO, (2) determine the level of acceptance of the stakeholder towards the VMGO, and (3) determine the determine perception of the stakeholder towards the VMGO.

Materials and Methods

Design

The descriptive survey method was employed in this study to determine the level of awareness, acceptance and perception of PSU Asingan faculty, staff, students, parents/ guardians, alumni, and other government agency partners towards the vision, mission, goals and objectives,

Materials

The Researchers adopted and modified the instrument developed Castillo in 2014 and enhanced by Oboza in 2017. It was also based on the 2010 AACUP Revised Instrument.

Respondents

This study included the faculty, staff, students, parents/ guardians, alumni, industry partners and other government agency partners of PSU Asingan Campus.

Table 1. PSU Asingan Stakeholders

Stakeholders	Frequency	Percentage
Faculty	33	9
Non-teaching	8	2
Students	289	79
Parents/ Guardians	7	2
Alumni	26	7
Other Government Agency Partner	2	1
Total	365	100.0

The respondents composed of students (79%), faculty (9%), alumni (7%), non-teaching staff and parents/ guardians (both 2%) and other government agencies (1%) with the total of three hundred sixty-five (365) respondents.

Among the student respondents, majority are third year (28%), then fourth year (26%), the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program students (14%) and the second year (8%).

Majority of the respondents are alumni/ students of Bachelor of Industrial Technology (45%), Bachelor Science of Business Administration (34%), Bachelor of Secondary Education (8%), Bachelor of Elementary Education (6%), Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (5%) and Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (2%).

Majority of the respondents are female (55%), male (42%) and three percent (3%) belong to the LGBTQ.

Majority of the respondents are Roman Catholic (69%), Born Again Christian (16%), Iglesia ni Cristo (8%), the Baptist, Methodist and Jesus Latter Day Saint (all in 2% each) and Seventh Day Adventist (1%).

Majority of the respondents' monthly household income are below P10, 000, they compose of 78%. The twelve percent (12%) of the respondents' monthly household income is P20,001 to P50,000; 8% of the respondents' monthly household income is P15,001 to P20,000 and 2% of the respondents' monthly household income is above P50,000.

Data Gathering and Analysis

Due to the new normal, the Researchers used the Google Form to administer the data gathering process among the PSU Asingan faculty, staff, students, parents/ guardians, alumni, industry partners and other government agency partners.

Data gathered were subjected to statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Specifically, frequency and mean were determined to measure the awareness, acceptance and perception of the stakeholders towards the VMGO.

The following scales were used to interpret the findings of the study:

Rating	Range	Awareness	Acceptance	Perception
4	3.50-4.00	Highly Aware (HA)	Greatly Accept (GA)	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.50-3.49	Aware (A)	Accept (A)	Agree (A)
2	1.50-2.49	Least Aware (LA)	Slightly Accept (SA)	Disagree (D)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Aware (NA)	Not Accept (NA)	Strongly disagree (SD)

The same scaling was used by Oboza in 2017.

Results and Discussion

I. Awareness on the VMGO

1. I am aware of the Vision and Mission of PSU

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	2	1
Least aware	13	4
Aware	211	58
Highly Aware	138	37
Total	364	100.0
Mean		3.33

Majority of the respondents are aware of the Vision and Mission of PSU.

2. I am aware of the Goals of PSU

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	3	1
Least aware	20	6
Aware	216	59
Highly Aware	126	34
Total	365	100.0
Mean		3.27

Majority of the respondents are aware of the Goals of PSU with the mean of 3.27.

3. I am aware of the Objectives of the program where I/ my/ child/ children belong.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	5	1
Least aware	28	8
Aware	222	62
Highly Aware	104	29
Total	359	100.0
Mean		3.18

Majority of the respondents are aware of the Objectives of the program where they belong.

II. Awareness on the VMGO Dissemination

1. I am aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	14	4
Least aware	55	15
Aware	201	56
Highly Aware	92	25
Total	362	100.0
Mean		3.02

Majority of the respondents, with the mean of 3.02, are aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards.

2. I am aware that the VGMO are printed in catalogs, manuals, and other materials.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	21	6
Least aware	54	15
Aware	198	54
Highly Aware	91	25
Total	364	100.0
Mean		2.98

Majority of the respondents, with the mean of 2.98, are aware that the VMGO are printed in catalogs, manuals, and other materials.

3. I am aware that the VGMO are broadcast in media and/ or internet/ website.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	17	5
Least aware	51	14
Aware	212	58
Highly Aware	83	23
Total	363	100.0
Mean		2.99

The majority of the respondents, with the mean of 2.99, are aware that the VGMO are broadcast in media and/ or internet/ website.

4. I am awareness that the VGMO are widely disseminated to different agencies, institutions, industry, and the community as a whole.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not aware	22	6
Least aware	71	20
Aware	206	56
Highly Aware	64	18
Total	363	100.0
Mean		2.85

Majority of the respondents, with the mean of 2.85, are aware that the VMGO are widely disseminated to different agencies, institutions, industry, and the community as a whole.

III. Understanding and Acceptance of the VMGO

1. I understand and accept the VMG of Pangasinan State University.

	Frequency	Percentage
Slight accept	24	7
Accept	205	56
Greatly Accept	135	37
Total	364	100.0
Mean		3.30

Majority of the respondents, with the mean of 3.30, understand and accept of VMG of Pangasinan State University.

2. I understand and accept the Goals of the Institution.

	Frequency	Percent
Slight accept	18	5
Accept	207	57
Greatly Accept	139	38
Total	364	100.0
Mean		3.33

Majority of the respondents, with the mean of 3.33, understand and accept the Goals of the Institution.

3. I understand and accept the Objectives of Program where I/ my/ child/ren belong and responsibility of PSU and others concerned in realizing such objectives.

	Frequency	Percentage
Slight accept	23	7
Accept	210	58
Greatly Accept	127	35
Total	360	100.0
Mean		3.28

Majority of the respondents understand and accept the Objectives of Program where they belong and responsibility of PSU and others concerned in realizing such objectives with the mean of 3.28.

IV. Perception towards VMGO's Clarity and Consistency

1. The Vision clearly reflects what PSU hopes to become in the future.

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	2	1
Agree	179	49
Strongly Agree	182	50
Total	363	100.0
Mean		3.49

Majority of the respondents strongly agree that the Vision clearly reflects what PSU hopes to become in the future.

2. The Mission clearly reflects PSU's legal and educational mandate.

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	2	1
Disagree	3	1
Agree	196	53
Strongly Agree	164	45
Total	365	100.0
Mean		3.43

Majority of the respondents agree that the Mission clearly reflects PSU's legal and educational mandate with the mean 3.43.

3. The Goals of the Institution are clearly stated and are consistent with the VMG of PSU.

	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	4	1
Agree	211	58
Strongly Agree	149	41
Total	364	100.0
Mean		3.39

Majority of the respondents agree that the Goals of the Institution are clearly stated and are consistent with the VMG of PSU with the mean 3.39.

4. The Program Objectives are consistent with the Goals of Asingan Campus and the University.

	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	211	58
Strongly Agree	151	42
Total	363	100.0
Mean		3.41

The respondents agree that the Program Objectives are consistent with the Goals of Asingan Campus and the University with the mean 3.41.

5. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcome in terms of competencies of technical skills of students and graduates.

	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	2	1
Agree	204	56
Strongly Agree	154	43
Total	361	100.0
System	4	3.41

Majority of the students agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcome in terms of competencies of technical skills of students and graduates with the mean 3.41.

6. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of research and extension capabilities of students and graduates.

	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	214	59
Strongly Agree	147	41
Total	364	100.0
Mean		3.39

Majority of the respondents agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of the research and extension capabilities of the students and graduates with the mean 3.39.

7. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of students' own ideas, desirable attitudes and personal discipline.

	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	4	1
Agree	208	57
Strongly Agree	150	42
Total	363	100.0
Mean		3.39

Majority of the respondents agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of students' own ideas, desirable attitudes and personal discipline with the mean of 3.39.

8. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of moral character

	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	223	62
Strongly Agree	136	38
Total	361	100.0
Mean		3.36

The respondents agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of moral character with the mean of 3.36.

9. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of critical thinking skills.

	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	4	1
Agree	213	59
Strongly Agree	144	40
Total	363	100.0
Mean		3.37

Majority of the respondents agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcomes in terms of critical thinking skills with the mean of 3.37.

10. The Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcome in terms of aesthetic and cultural values.

	Frequency	Percentage
Disagree	5	2
Agree	214	59
Strongly Agree	141	39
Total	361	100.0
Mean		3.37

The respondents agree that the Program Objectives clearly state the expected outcome in terms of aesthetic and cultural values with the mean of 3.37.

Conclusions

Based on the Findings the following are concluded:

- 1) the stakeholders are aware of the VMGO,
- 2) the stakeholders understand and accept the VMGO, and
- 3) the stakeholders agree that the VMGO is clear and consistent

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions the following are recommended:

- 1) The University and the Campus should take extra efforts in disseminating the VMGOs to the stakeholders.
- 2) Widen information drive could be on radio, local television network and social media platforms.
- 3) The Faculty and Staff should activity participate in the dissemination of the VMGO.
- 4) The University officials, faculty and staff should take extra effort to implement and sustain the University VMGO.

References

Republic Act 7722: Higher Education Act of 1994

Outcome-based Instrument for Bachelor of Industrial Technology by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities of the Philippines (AACCU), Inc. (2014)